

THE INFLUENCE OF SELF-REGULATION AND SOCIAL MEDIA EXPOSURE ON RESILIENCE AMONG YOUNG ADULTS

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Abstract

In today's Digital world, people tend to balance their dealings with digital things. Social media has a highlighted impact on life, so understanding what helps young people be strong is important. Matching self-control with using digital platforms might facilitate young people do well. The present study aimed to investigate the Influence of Self-regulation and Social Media Exposure on Resilience among Young Adults. (aged 29-24), including both males and females from colleges and universities, participated in the study. It was a Correlational Cross-sectional study. Data were collected using a demographic form, the Short Self-Regulation Scale (SSRS) (Carey et al.2004), the Social Media Use Scale (SMUS), and the Nicholson McBride Resilience Questionnaire (NMRQ). Data analysis included the Pearson Product Moment Correlation test to explore relationships and Independent Samples T-test for gender differences and Linear regression for predictive effects, and. The findings were expected to offer valuable insights into how internal self-control and external digital exposure influence resilience. The study held implications for designing interventions aimed at promoting mental well-being and adaptive functioning in young adults, along with suggestions for future research.

INTRODUCTION

The transition of becoming adult is connected with considerable emotional, social and psychological adjustments and most of the time it is put into test due to the challenges that young adults have to face during adult transition. The core in their well-being is resilience, which is the power to overcome a crisis. In the modern world of technology, media bombardment determines the way young adults develop emotion management, stress responses and resilience. The fact that self-regulation is one of the components of emotional intelligence makes it possible to keep thoughts, emotions, and actions under control. The problem is that the influence of media exposure on the self-regulation and resilience is not thoroughly comprehended. The paper investigates the relationship between self-regulation, media exposure, and resilience among young adults in an effort to guide evidence-based interventions that supports mental wellness as well as coping abilities in this crucial developmental phase. Bandura (Bandura, 1991) highlights three main components of self-regulative mechanism:

1. Self-observation (self-monitoring of one's behavior, its determinants and effects)
2. Judgment of one's behaviour in relation to personal standards and environmental circumstances. Affective self-reaction (Bandura, 1991). There are three basic components of Self-regulation: The first is commitment to standards. The second is monitoring of the self and its behaviours. The third is what is needed to change the self's responses. All are necessary for effective self-regulation. Hence a breakdown or problem with any one of them can produce failure at self-regulation" (Baumeister, Schmeichel & Vohs, 2007)

Individuals use social media for a variety of reasons including entertainment, identity formation, and social enhancement and maintaining interpersonal connections (Ifinedo, 2016). Research shows the psychological factors associated with problematic internet use among adults, specifically focusing on the roles of happiness, psychological resilience, dispositional hope, self-control, and self-management. These findings suggest that higher levels of these positive psychological traits are associated with reduced problematic internet use in adults.

Additionally, self-control and self-management were found to have an indirect effect on problematic internet use, with happiness, psychological resilience, and dispositional hope serving as mediators. The results highlight the importance of enhancing adults' emotional well-being and self-regulatory capacities as a means to mitigate problematic internet behaviors, and the study concludes with practical recommendations for reducing such use through psychological interventions. (Yilmaz & Karaoglan, 2022)

Media-system Dependency Theory was proposed by Sandra Ball-Rokeach and Melvin DeFleur in 1976. It posits that the foundation of media influence lies in the relationships among the social system, media system, and audience system. The dynamism and complexity of the social environment, along with the resulting uncertainty, lead individuals to rely on the informational resources provided by the media to comprehend society. This dependency results in individuals' social cognition and attitudes being significantly influenced by the media system. Cultivation theory was proposed by George Gerbner in the 1960s. Focuses on how

the amount of television that is taken in impacts the perceptions and attitudes of the watcher. Gratifications Theory was first systematically outlined by Elihu Katz, Jay G. Blumler, and Michael Gurevitch in the 1970s. It is based on users actively attempting to satisfy their media needs. Elihu Katz is often credited with being one of the original creators of this theory. This theory states that an individual will choose the media or form of media that will satisfy their desires most completely. There are a number of different desires involved with this theory, such as a desire for information or social interaction. When seeking to fulfil these desires, an individual will need to make a decision. A research revealed that excessive screen media use is linked to poor sleep quality, reduced sleep duration, higher risks of overweight and obesity, diminished executive functioning, lower academic performance, and increased internalizing and externalizing behavioural issues. (Liu et al, 2021) However the decision making process becomes more convoluted when deciding between watching a movie, playing a game online, or reading a newspaper. The same fundamental principle applies however, the

person will make the decision based on what brings the most gratification.

Resilience is defined as the process of effectively negotiating, adapting to, or managing significant sources of stress or trauma. Individuals seeking to regain control of the situation are likely to use the resources not affected by the crisis to install stability (Masten, 2018; Vindevogel, 2017). Developmental Systems Theory of Resilience Ann Masten (2001) proposed that resilience arises from “ordinary magic” everyday systems such as relationships, problem-solving abilities, and self-regulation. Her Developmental Systems Theory highlights resilience as a normative human capacity supported by developmental assets. (Masten, 2018). Research showed the relationship between social media use and the development of resilience and coping abilities among late adolescents and emerging adults aged 18 to 24. This study contributes to the field of Developmental Psychology by addressing existing gaps in the literature regarding how social media engagement may influence coping styles and resilience in this age group. These findings suggest that, contrary to common

assumptions, social media engagement alone may not be a determining factor in shaping how late adolescents develop resilience or manage stress. (Breen & Bethany, 2024)

LITERATURE REVIEW

Attai (2021) aimed to explore the relationship between self-regulation and academic resilience, with perceived competence as a mediator, among 360 undergraduate students in Tehran. The results showed that self-regulation directly predicted academic resilience, and perceived competence mediated this relationship, enhancing resilience. The findings suggest that fostering self-regulation and perceived competence can facilitate academic resilience, enabling students to navigate challenging situations and prevent academic failure.

Qamaria. et.al (2025) conducted a study aimed at exploring the conceptual development of digital resilience (DR) in adolescents. The results revealed that digital resilience is understood as an individual's ability to safeguard themselves and recover from harmful experiences encountered online. While mixed methods,

qualitative designs, and literature reviews are prevalent in digital resilience research, quantitative studies remain limited, particularly those involving adolescent populations. The ecological theory framework is frequently applied to explain DR, and three conceptual models were identified—two of which still require empirical validation. The study highlights the increasing significance of digital resilience in the context of adolescent online experiences and provides direction for future empirical investigations targeting adolescent populations.

Sage et al (2020) explored how a resilience framework can enhance social workers' understanding of mitigating risks faced by youth using Internet and Communication Technologies (ICTs). The findings suggest that social work interventions targeting resilience could effectively reduce risks for youth engaged with ICTs. However, resilience remains inconsistently defined across studies, highlighting the need for more rigorous research, especially concerning marginalized youth.

López-Martínez et al. (2025) investigated the associations between non-suicidal self-injurious

behaviour (NSSI) and various psychological and behavioural factors, including emotional self-regulation strategies, substance use, dependence on social networks, and emotional symptomatology among adolescents. Results revealed that increased symptomatology and substance use were significant predictors of NSSI for both genders, while maladaptive self-regulation strategies were particularly associated with NSSI in girls. The model used was able to accurately classify 89.5% of boys who did not self-harm and 72.8% of girls who did. These findings underscore the complex interplay between emotional regulation, digital behaviour, substance use, and mental health in adolescent self-harm depending on social networks, with a particular emphasis on gender differences.

Wang & Mao (2025) investigated how college students' social support seeking on social networking sites (SNSs) relates to their psychological resilience, focusing on activities and interactions on Douyin (TikTok's counterpart in China). The findings highlight that the benefits of social support on psychosocial well-being depend on specific SNS activities and social connections, offering

nuanced insights into how digital interactions support adolescent health.

Canaslan and Sungur (2022) investigated the self-regulation skills of children aged 4 to 6 in relation to their digital media usage. The results revealed a clear negative association between the amount of time spent on digital media and children's self-regulation abilities children who used digital media more frequently exhibited lower levels of self-regulation. Furthermore, exposure to violent or horror-themed content was linked to poorer self-regulation, while children who engaged with educational or foreign language content showed higher self-regulation scores. These findings underscore the influence of digital media habits on young children's developmental outcomes and highlight the critical role of parents in managing both the quantity and quality of media exposure to support healthy self-regulation development.

Zmavc et al. (2022) examined the psychometric properties of the Slovenian version of the Bergen Social Media Addiction Scale and to investigate the direct and indirect effects of psychological resilience on social media addiction symptoms through depression, anxiety,

and mental distress. Findings confirmed the high reliability, unidimensionality, and criterion validity of the scale. Structural model analysis revealed that depression and stress had a significant direct positive effect on social media addiction, while psychological resilience primarily influenced addiction symptoms indirectly—87.2% of its protective effect operated through reducing depression and stress, with a smaller impact observed through anxiety reduction.

HYPOTHESIS

1. There is likely to be a significant relationship in Self-regulation and Social Media Exposure on Resilience among Young Adults.
2. There is likely to be a significant relationship in Social Media Exposure on Resilience among Young Adults.
3. There are likely to be gender differences in Resilience among Young Adults.
4. Self-regulation and social media exposure are likely to be the predictors of resilience among young adults.

METHODOLOGY

Sample Design Correlational Cross-sectional research design was used in the present study to

assess the relationship between Self-regulation and Social Media Exposure on Resilience among Young Adults Participants and Sampling strategy Sample was recruited for data collection according to inclusion and exclusion criteria. The sample of 100 young adults was recruited. The sample include both male and female with age range of 19 to 24 years' regular students. The participant's demographics are mentioned in Demographics (table 1). Non- probability purposive sampling strategy was used to recruit participants.

MEASURES

INFORMED CONSENT FORM

The participants were explained about the purpose behind the conduction of the study in the informed consent form, and they were asked for their voluntary participation. Moreover, their signature for their participation was also be included in this form.

DEMOGRAPHIC INFORMATION FORM

Demographic form included age, gender, education, birth order, family structure, Social class, marital status.

Short Self-regulation Scale: The 31-item SSRQ is a short version of the original SSRQ (Brown,

Miller & Lewandowsky, 1999). This scale yielded a single factor solution in a sample of American undergraduate students, with a Cronbach's alpha of .92 for the total scale score. (Carey et al.2004) Social Media Exposure Social Media Use (SMUS) scale, reliability ($\alpha = 0.844$) refers to the consistency and dependability of the scale's measures in assessing social media use. It essentially indicates how much the scale produces similar results when measuring the same construct (social media use) across multiple administrations or different sets of items. It is based on 17 items . **Nicholson McBride Resilience Questionnaire (NMRQ)** Is is a 12 item measure on resilience, created by McBride. It is measured on a five point likert scale, ranging 22 from 'strongly disagree' to 'strongly agree'. Scores 0-37 a Developing Level of Resilience, Scores 38 -43 Indicate an Established Level of Resilience, Scores 44 -48 Indicate A Strong Level of Resilience and Scores 49 -60 Indicate an Exceptional Level of Resilience. The Reliability Estimated by Cronbach's Alpha = .76 (Nicholson McBride, 2019).

PROCEDURE

First of all, synopsis was approved from the institute. After this approval, permission will be taken from authors of the scales and the use of these scales in the present study. After this, permission letters for the data collection will be issued and signed from the supervisor and Director of the Institute. Consent will be taken from the participants. A general overview of the research purpose will be briefly described to the participants. Instructions regarding the questionnaire would be provided to the

participants and they will be informed that their confidentiality would be maintained. Participants will be informed about the ethical rights that they can use during the research, as in withdrawal from the research at any point of the time. It will take approximately 15 minutes on average to fill a questionnaire. After the data collection, the data will be entered in SPSS and will be analysed according to the hypothesis and analysis.

RESULTS

TABLE 1

Descriptive Statistical and Result of Independent t test of mean difference of Gender (men and women) the relationship between Self-regulation

and Social Media Exposure on Resilience among Young Adults.

Variable	Male	Female	t(df)	p	Cohen's d
	M(SD)	M(SD)			
Resilience	42.5(4.62)	41.4(4.88)	.937	.351	0.23

Note M=mean, SD=, standard deviation

Table 1 shows, the gender differences in resilience are non-significant as $p > .05$, male (M=42.5, SD= 4.62) and female (M=41.4, SD=4.88). The effect size of the resilience is denoted by Cohen d is 0.23. Finding indicate no gender diversity exit in resilience among young

adults. It was hypothesized that there is likely to be a positive significant relationship between Self- regulation and Resilience among Young Adults. Then the following analysis shows in below.

TABLE 2: DESCRIPTIVE STATISTICS AND CORRELATIONS FOR STUDY VARIABLES

Variable	n	M	SD	1	2
Self-Regulation	100	109.2	12.74	-	
Resilience	100	41.77	4.81	.373**	-

Note = N= sample (N=100), M=mean, SD=standard deviation, p>0.01.

The results revealed that there is statistically positive significant relationship between Self-regulation (IV) and Resilience (DV) among Young Adults with scores $r = .373^{**}$, $p > 0.01$ at the level of $p .01^{**}$. It suggested that higher level

of self-Regulation are associated with greater level of Resilience. This correlation is statistically significant at level of .01, indicate significant relationship between Self-Regulation (IV) and Resilience (DV)'

TABLE 4: DESCRIPTIVE STATISTICS AND CORRELATIONS FOR STUDY VARIABLES

Variable	n	M	SD	1	2
Social Media Exposure	100	47.47	21.08	-	
Resilience	150	41.77	4.81	-.192**	-

Note= N= sample (N=100), M=mean, SD=standard deviation, $p < .01^{**}$.

The results revealed that there is statistically negative significant relationship between Social Media Exposure (IV) and Resilience(DV) among Young Adults with scores $r = -.192$, $p > 0.01^{**}$ at the level of $p .01^{**}$. It suggested that

associated with greater level of Resilience. This correlation is statistically significant at level of .01, indicate negative significant relation between Social Media Exposure (IV) and Resilience (DV)

higher level of Social Media Exposure are

TABLE 5: DESCRIPTIVE STATISTICS AND CORRELATIONS FOR STUDY VARIABLES

Variable	n	M	SD	1	2	3
Self-Regulation	100	109.2	12.74	-		
Social Media Exposure	100	47.47	21.08	-.472**		
Resilience	150	41.77	4.81	.373**	-.192	-

The results revealed that there is statistically positive significant relationship between Self-

regulation (IV) and Resilience (DV) among Young Adults with scores $r = .373^{**}$, $p > 0.01$ at

the level of $p < .01^{**}$.while statistically positive significant relationship between Self-regulation (IV) and Resilience (DV) among Young Adults with scores $r = .373^{**}$, $p > 0.01$ at the level of $p < .01^{**}$.It suggested that higher level of self-Regulation are associated with greater level of

Resilience. This correlation is statistically significant at level of .01,indicate significant relationship between Self-Regulation (IV) and Resilience (DV)there is also a strong negative relation between social media exposure and self-regulation, $r = -.472$ at $p < 0.01^{**}$.

TABLE 4: LINEAR REGRESSION SHOWING PREDICTING EFFECT OF SELF-REGULATION, SOCIAL MEDIA EXPOSURE ON RESILIENCE AMONG YOUNG ADULTS

Predictors	Resilience		
	B	β	SE
Self-Regulation	.137	.363	.041
Social Media Exposure	-.005	-.021	.025
ΔR^2	.139		

Table 4 shows the overall regression model is significant with R^2 value of .139 revealed that the predictor variable explained 1.3% variance in the outcome variable with $F(15.64)$ $p < 0.001^{***}$. The standardized beta coefficient for social media exposure predicting resilience was $\beta = -.021$ Multiple linear regression was used to find out the predictor of resilience among young adults. Table reveals that self- Regulation was the predictor of risk-taking behaviour at $p < .001^{***}$.

It was hypothesized that there is likely to be a significant relationship in Self-regulation and Social Media Exposure on Resilience among Young Adults. Study examined whether self-regulation predicts social networking site (SNS) addiction, with academic resilience and psychological well-being as mediators, in high school students. Findings revealed that self-regulation significantly and negatively predicted SNS addiction, and while academic resilience did not directly mediate this relationship, it indirectly affected SNS addiction through psychological well-being. These results support

DISCUSSION

the role of self-regulation in managing the negative impact of social media use and enhancing resilience through improved psychological well-being. (Manzari et al., 2024)

It was hypothesized that there is likely to be a significant relationship in Social Media Exposure on Resilience among Young Adult. Study explored the relationship between social support- seeking behaviors on social networking sites (SNSs) and psychological resilience among Chinese college students. The study found that active SNS engagement, especially communication with familiar peers, positively influenced resilience. This highlights how specific types of social media interactions can enhance young adults' coping abilities and emotional strength. (Wang & Mao, 2025)

It was hypothesized that there are likely to be gender differences in Resilience among Young Adults and this study investigated the effects of cyber peer violence on adolescents' emotion regulation and socioemotional adjustment, focusing on the mediating role of resilience. Results showed notable gender differences: females exhibited higher resilience and emotional responsiveness but also experienced

greater emotional distress when victimized. In contrast, males were more often perpetrators and less emotionally affected. This study underscores the gender-specific patterns in resilience development and psychological adjustment. (Gianesini & Brighi, 2015)

Whole discussion revealed that there is a significant relationship among self-Regulation, social media exposure and resilience among adults and it also highlights the significant role of self- regulation and social media exposure in shaping resilience among young adults. International and indigenous studies consistently show that self-regulation positively predicts resilience across diverse contexts, including academic, vocational, and athletic settings. Additionally, perceived competence enhances this relationship, further strengthening resilience. In the context of social media, its impact on resilience is complex, with both beneficial and detrimental effects depending on usage patterns and external circumstances. Overall, fostering self-regulation skills and understanding the nuanced influence of social media are crucial for enhancing resilience in young adults.

The present study has great contributions for the literature work. As result shown, there is strong relation between self-Regulation, social media exposure and resilience among adults. To manage resilience level in young adults, counselling programs should be organized to support and understand they're on strength and power of positivity for mental peace as result shows that there is negative relationship on media exposure and resilience level. Gratitude also enhances the satisfaction level in adults, as result shows that there is negative relationship between social media exposure and resilience feeling.so such programs should also be organized that make adults aware of the significance of self-regulation.

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